

Berkshire Health Inequalities Group

Connected Care Project Report

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Executive Summary

Purpose: An online survey was commissioned and conducted to capture lived experiences of healthcare access and inequality from residents across Berkshire to inform service improvement across the NHS, local authorities, and the voluntary sector.

Sample: 115 respondents; majority working-age adults; a substantial proportion reporting disability or long-term conditions.

Key findings:

- Access to GP services is a major barrier, particularly for disabled people and those with complex needs.
- Telephone congestion and digital-only triage systems are the most frequently reported obstacles.
- Many working adults report compromising their health due to inflexible appointment systems.
- Respondents describe a postcode lottery in service quality and availability.
- Free-text responses highlight feelings of dismissal, fragmentation, and exhaustion navigating care.

Implications: Inequalities are driven by system design rather than individual behaviour, requiring coordinated, place-based responses. More detailed recommendations, together with the organisations who should own the responsibility for each of them, are at the end of this report.

Introduction

The Connected Care Project was initially set up by the Berkshire Health Inequalities Group (BHIG) to support the introduction of new datasets into the Connected Care Database as run by the NHS in the Thames Valley region. It had been hoped that it would be possible to introduce new data from local authorities and voluntary and charitable organisations working within the health and social care sector in the Thames Valley region. Although there was much willingness to form new partnerships and data sharing agreements to incorporate new data sets into Connected Care, it became apparent that this would not be possible to do under current organisational structures as anonymised postcode level data cannot be accepted into Connected Care. All data introduced into Connected Care would need to be matched with service users'/clients'/patients' NHS numbers. This is a current barrier due to the need to strengthen data sharing agreements between partners, create strict protocols to protect shared data and ensure that patient confidentiality is maintained at all times, plus the aim was to reach clients and service users who may not have an NHS number. There is also the current risk that the prospect of sharing data with the NHS from select partners, such as drug and alcohol services, could hinder the likelihood of people seeking out and accepting help for their substance misuse issues if they are fearful of their data being shared with the NHS. In order to create these new data sharing agreements new staff would need to be hired (data analysts etc) to maintain this new data sharing through monthly cleaning and matching of data before it is incorporated into the Connected Care database.

Due to the aforementioned issues, the aims of the Connected Care project changed somewhat. Instead of focusing on incorporating new data sets into Connected Care the same end point could potentially be reached by using machine learning and large language models to co-analyse separate data sets without physically merging them; however this is beyond the scope of the present project and would be the subject of a future external funding application. Meanwhile, the Connected Care project pivoted to undertake a survey and some focus group work to find out what kind of barriers people face in Berkshire when they try to access NHS healthcare.

The study received ethical approval from the School of Chemistry, Food and Pharmacy at the University of Reading and was given study number SREC 22/2025. Participants were provided with a Participant Information Sheet and provided consent prior to starting the survey. Participants could withdraw from the survey at any time. The survey was available online and in paper format. The online survey was shared with various local groups via social media (e.g. local Facebook groups such as 'Reading Gossip Girls', 'Reading, Berkshire UK Group', 'Newbury Group', 'Bracknell News and Events' etc) and through advertisements placed in emailed and paper newsletters with local community groups. Paper copies of the survey were also made available through local

community groups such as council run children’s centres, mental health charities and language support groups.

In total there were 115 unique responses to the survey (total includes online and paper submissions).

Focus groups were run with local community organisations such as charitable mental health and social wellbeing support groups and language support groups. Although many attempts were made to engage with men in the focus groups, unfortunately only women’s organisations provided access to complete the focus group work. A total of 15 women took part in the focus groups. Their focus group work and feedback has been turned into an e-book which can be viewed here: <https://tinyurl.com/bdf9mhxs>

This report is focused on the responses to the survey and should be read in conjunction with the above linked e-book.

Demographics

Out of a total of 115 survey respondents, 110 provided either their age or the age of the person they care for. The mean age was 48.68, median age was 47.5 and the range was 4-87 years old (Figure 1). Please note that the minimum age of 4 years relates to a very young child and this suggests that at least one response to this survey was likely completed by a parent or carer.

Figure 1. Age distribution of survey respondents (n=110).

As can be seen from Figure 1, the majority of survey responses came from participants who were of working age. This suggests that the access to healthcare barriers captured here are particularly relevant to economically active adults, carers, and those managing long-term conditions alongside work.

Overwhelmingly more women than men or transgender/non-binary people responded to the survey (Figure 2). Out of 115 responses 97 were from women, 15 were from men and 3 were from people who identify as transgender:

Figure 2. Gender identity of survey respondents (n=115).

There was a nearly even split between respondents who reported that they were or were not disabled, with 55% stating they were not disabled and 45% stating that they were disabled (Figure 3). Disabled respondents appear across all age groups, not just older cohorts. This allowed robust comparison between disabled vs non-disabled experiences, particularly around access to GP services, feeling supported and navigating appointments and referrals.

Figure 3. Disability status of survey respondents (n=115).

Of the respondents who stated that they did have a disability, 30% reported a long-term illness, 24% reported mobility issues and 20% reported a mental health diagnosis (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Disability type of survey respondents who reported living with disability (n=115).

In terms of employment status, the majority of survey respondents stated that they were in some form of employment, whether that was full-time, part-time or self-employment (Figure 5). Importantly, many respondents experiencing healthcare access problems in this survey are in work, which challenges the assumption that barriers are limited to economically inactive groups.

Figure 5. Employment status of survey respondents (n=112).

There was a wide range of reported yearly household income of survey respondents, this highlights the wide-ranging income disparities of people living in the Berkshire area (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Household income reported by survey respondents (n=112).

Healthcare access problems appeared across income groups which suggests that they are caused by structural and systemic barriers and not just affordability issues. Respondents to the survey reported a range of highest level of qualification with almost one third reporting having a bachelor's degree or higher (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Highest level of qualification reported by survey respondents (n=111).

The majority of respondents reported living in stable accommodation (82.6%) with 13.8% reporting that they were worried about their housing situation, 2.8% reported living in emergency accommodation and 0.9% reported that they did not have any housing (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Housing status of survey respondents (n=109).

Out of all survey respondents, 35 (nearly one third) reported household maintenance issues with the properties they were living in which all have health implications for those living in the properties (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Reported household maintenance issues from survey respondents (n=33).

Respondents were asked if they could share their home postcode. Not all respondents did but the following shows the data that is available (Figure 10):

Figure 10. Distribution of survey respondents by postcode (n=108). RG indicates Reading area, SL indicates Slough area.

Respondents were asked to give an overall rating to the NHS with 5 stars representing 'excellent' and 1 star representing 'very poor'. The majority of respondents rated the NHS as 'average' (Figure 11).

How would you rate the overall quality of the care that you receive from the NHS?

Figure 11. Overall rating of the NHS by survey respondents (n=115).

Access to NHS Services for Physical Healthcare Needs

The first half of the survey asked respondents questions about how they viewed access to NHS services such as GP care and hospital care for their physical healthcare needs. Respondents were asked if they had a diagnosis of a long-term physical condition and 53% responded that they did, with the following physical health conditions being reported (Figure 12):

Figure 12. Word cloud of most commonly reported conditions from survey respondents who reported experiencing a long-term physical health condition (n=61).

The most commonly reported physical conditions were arthritis, fibromyalgia, diabetes, back pain, asthma and osteoarthritis.

Participants were then asked how easy they found it to access GP services for their physical healthcare needs. The majority of respondents stated that they found it ‘somewhat difficult’ to access GP services (Figure 13):

. How easy is it for you to access GP services for your physical healthcare needs?

Figure 13. Reported ease of access to GP services for physical healthcare needs (n=112).

When asked how well supported they felt by their GP practice, the majority of participants (57%) stated that they felt their GP practice only ‘sometimes’ provided them with a good level of support (Figure 14):

Do you feel well supported by your GP practice?

Figure 14. Level of support experienced by users from their GP practice (n=115).

Further data analysis was carried out to ascertain how gender and disability affects answers to these questions. It was found that people who answered ‘yes’ to the question asking them if they had a disability were more likely to state that they found accessing GP services ‘somewhat difficult’ (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Ease of accessing GP for physical health treatment by disability status (n=91).

Gender disparities were also recorded which showed that women are more likely to experience difficulties in accessing GP services compared to men (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Impact of gender on perceived ease of accessing GP appointments (n=92).

When looking at how disability status and gender affect how supported respondents felt by their GP practice the respondents who answered ‘yes’ to the question asking if they were disabled were more likely to say ‘sometimes’ and a lower proportion felt supported all the time compared to respondents who did not report experiencing disability (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Impact of disability on feelings of being supported by GP practice (n=91).

When analysing how gender impacted on how supported respondents felt by their GP practice, an interesting gender disparity was found. Whereas women were more likely to report difficulties in accessing GP support as shown above, it was men who answered ‘no, never’ when asked how well supported they felt by their GP practice (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Impact of gender on how well supported survey respondents felt by their GP practice (n=92).

The majority of respondents across all genders and gender identities answered that they only ‘sometimes’ felt well supported by their GP practice which suggests that this is a widespread issue.

The following barriers were reported by respondents as being the main reasons why they struggle to access GP care (Figure 19):

Figure 19. Reported barriers to accessing GP services (n=115).

Respondents were then offered a free text box to detail what they think would help them better access GP services. The most frequent responses were the need for more GP's, more flexible opening hours to cover evenings and weekends, less reliance on a rigid online triage system which people struggle to complete and the ability to consistently see the same GP. Quotes include:

“Appointments outside of work hours would be great.”

“Offering bookable appointments for non urgent issues so those who work can plan their time better. Increasing number of GP's.”

“More GP's in the area”

“More appointments, more time to get to appointments, when they reply to triage with a time it's very short notice”

“The ability to book online appointments with all health care professionals and select a convenient date and time without having to go through triage first. I think it should be compulsory for the patient to give a reason for the appointment. The health care

professionals can message back if they think the medical issue should be directed elsewhere.”

“As a minimum, it would help if I could write emails directly to my GP and have the same GP consistently.”

“Unfortunately, none of the GP’s work full time (it’s very rare) so issues usually arise when you cannot get continuity of care with the same GP.”

“Remove the compulsory use of online systems which push you down incorrect routes and cause frustration and delay. Remove the barriers around mentioning multiple issues in one appointment. When you struggle to get appointments multiple issues arise over time so they should all be discussed and being forced to chose one problem per appointment is counterproductive and could prove lethal. Patients cant decide what is or isn’t important or relevant.”

Survey respondents were then asked how easy they felt it was for them to access hospital based care for their physical healthcare needs (Figure 20). The majority of respondents stated that they found accessing hospital based healthcare ‘neither easy or difficult’ (30%):

. How easy is it for you to access hospital based NHS healthcare for your physical needs?

Figure 20. Reported ease of accessing hospital-based care by survey respondents (n=115).

When asked about what sort of barriers people face, the following answers were given (Figure 21):

Figure 21. Barriers to hospital-based care reported by survey respondents (n=115).

Most notably, the length of hospital waiting lists were reported to be the most common barrier, closely followed by respondents reporting that they struggle to get GPs to refer them to hospital.

Survey respondents were then given a free text box in which they could write suggestions of what they think would better help them access hospital services. The free text comments most notably made reference to the long waiting lists, issues with getting GPs to agree to refer to hospital, not being believed by doctors, parking issues at hospitals and the lack of an easy mechanism for patients to chase up referrals:

“Being referred when asked. Treating the problem instead of the reasons”

“If GP would consider straight away to send to hospital to get more test, it should not be ignored for a nearly year”

“Proper understanding of needs by the GP surgery. Often don’t get to see a qualified GP only a practitioner who I have had guessing at causes.”

“Easier access to GPs who actually have time to listen and consider the best next steps, including further testing”

“Parking at RBH is a barrier for access”

“Parking costs and lack of parking”

“To be able to chase up a referral if no action”

“More funding into hospitals, and medical staff that take women seriously. Particularly young women”

Mental Health and Neurodiversity

The next section of the questionnaire asked respondents about what barriers they face when trying to access both GP and hospital based healthcare for their mental health, learning disability and neurodiversity needs. Not all respondents chose to answer questions in this section.

Respondents were first asked if they have a diagnosis of a mental health, learning disability or neurodiversity (Figure 22).

Do you have a diagnosis of a mental health condition and/or learning disability/neurodiversity?

Figure 22. Reported experience of mental healthcare, learning disability or neurodiversity by survey respondents (n=110).

Of the respondents who stated that they did have a relevant diagnosis, the most common diagnosis was autism and anxiety (both 24%), closely followed by depression (21%) (Figure 23). Only 4% of respondents stated that they had a mental health diagnosis that qualifies as a Serious Mental Illness (SMI). Further work would need to be done to explore the barriers experienced by those with an SMI qualifying diagnosis.

Figure 23. Reported mental health, learning difficulty or neurodiversity from survey respondents (n=39).

When asked how easy respondents felt it was to access GP healthcare for their mental health, learning disability or neurodiversity needs, most respondents stated that it was ‘neither easy nor difficult’ (43%) but 27% reported access being ‘somewhat difficult’ or ‘very difficult’. This suggests clear barriers that exist when such patients attempt to access GP healthcare (Figure 24).

How easy is it for you to access GP services for your mental health and/or learning disability/neurodiversity healthcare needs?

Figure 24. Perceived ease of accessing GP mental healthcare reported by survey respondents (n=61).

Male and transgender representation in the respondents was very low, so the following data were analysed in more detail for female respondents only to see how they experience barriers when trying to access GP healthcare for their mental health, learning disability and/or neurodiversity needs (Figures 25 and 26).

Figure 25. Female respondent experience of accessing GP healthcare for mental health, learning difficulty and neurodiversity (n=36).

The data were then analysed to see how females experience barriers when trying to access hospital-based healthcare for their mental health, learning disability and/or neurodiversity needs (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Female experience of accessing hospital-based care for respondents with mental health, learning difficulty or neurodiversity needs (n=36).

Respondents were then given the opportunity to state what they think would help them to access hospital-based services for their mental health, learning disability and/or neurodiversity needs by typing their response in a free text box. Most responses stated the need for more funding for more staff and for staff to be less dismissive of patients requesting help:

“Only option is talking therapy which isn’t helpful for complex cases”

“I was never provided hospital level mental health care and support. Just loaded with pills and counselling once in few years”

“I waited for 6 months for a Talking Therapies assessment. I waited a further 6 months for an appointment. I had an extended 12 sessions with Talking Therapies and was told my sessions had to stop due to NHS constraints. I went back to my GP and my GP advocated for me as they didn’t feel it was acceptable to not give me other options. I then received an incredibly insensitive and judgmental letter from the CMHT team, completely invalidating my experience with the only suggestion to have privately funded therapy.”

“Doctors feel once given prescription then its ok to leave patient on mental health medication for years and ignore when patient complains about weight gain and wants to stop medication”

“We need less GP's offering medication before getting to the root of the problem”

“Better trained counsellors and workers on the CMHT. Increased funding for these services.”

“Access to immediate help for mental health crisis. Reduced waiting lists and some GP’s not gaslighting symptoms.”

“Shorter waiting times”

“Well if doctors viewed mental health as a very important part of our overall health and offered other interventions not only pharmaceutical approaches to provide struggling patients the care they desperately need.”

“Although the NHS advertises support available and reasonable adjustments it does not work in practice therefore important tests and procedures are not carried out putting disabled person at risk. Annual health checks are tick box exercises, no support once health issue identified and no health action plan.”

“Support for everyone not just certain categories of mental health. Neurodiversity services non existent”

The final two questions of the survey asked respondents what they thought the biggest barriers to achieving healthcare equality in the UK are and also provided respondents with a free text box to write any final thoughts they wanted to share.

In answer to the question about what the biggest barriers to achieving healthcare equality in the UK, the majority of respondents stated that they believed our NHS healthcare services receive insufficient funding (Figure 27).

In your opinion, what is the biggest barrier to achieving healthcare equality in the UK? (please select all that apply)

Figure 27. Summary of responses from survey respondents about the barriers to healthcare equity (n=57).

In the final free text box, survey respondents had the following final thoughts to share about NHS services in Berkshire:

“Treatment shouldn’t depend on where you live I shouldn’t have to ask for funding to a clinic that takes me two hrs to drive to!”

“As a working individual I feel I am compromising my health because the system does not support me to maintain my job while I’m seeking medical support”

“I have been waiting for nearly year with my 6 years old child, the child was in pain screaming and GP have not even done any further test apart urine, it took me 11 months to going back and forward to get further test which was poo test. The waiting list was extremely long it's took us 21 months to get diagnosis, which is ridiculous especially if you have a child in constant pain.”

“Employ more workers or have a mental health team at GP surgeries”

“A&E is overcrowded partly because people can’t speak to/see their doctors. Also too many people trying to access a service that hasn’t increased in line with population. Look at increase of population in Reading in last 20 + years v NHS services and facilities. Smaller hospitals such as Battle, Dellwood closed down and we still have Royal Berks on same site. No increase in NHS in Reading to accommodate huge increase in population”

“Too much health care now requires visiting a large hospital for even simple issues. A system of local clinics would take a great number of cases out of the hi-tech, v costly and overwhelmed hospital system and make it easier for patients to see someone quickly”

“Listen to the patient. They know their bodies. We may not be medically trained. However we do know when something is not right with us. We also know when we are being fobbed off to avoid the waiting lists growing at the hospitals.”

“Simply put, deaf people are worse off because we miss the essential information that needs to be imparted to us in an appropriate way. I had to rely on a female chaperone nurse to tell me what the gynaecologist was saying - I couldn't Lipread his strong accent. That's difficult in a very private 'women's parts' consultation! I was glad of the nurse! But it wasn't her role.”

“West Berkshire has a large rural population whilst its hospital care facilities are all focused at one end of the area. Poor public transport impacts access to healthcare for many people in rural areas and there are far more inequalities present here than people imagine looking at the surface of an affluent area.”

“The funding for GP practices is appalling and is putting locum GPs out of work and recruiting associated professions with less training/experience. This is a patient safety issue.”

“As a woman I was mistreated , gaslighted, dismissed . It is a well known fact that women get given a label “emotional”, “anxious” etc instead of validating their physical symptoms. Simple female health is also non existent- no regular access to doctors or nurses keep a good eye on our female health - very shocking comparing to EU state healthcare services.”

“Young women need to be believed and not dismissed!”

“Berkshire Oxfordshire and Hampshire all only provide IVF funding until age 35, whilst all other areas in the UK provide it until 40 or 42. How is this fair? As a 36 year old woman with fertility issues, why am I being penalised for living in this geographic area. I'm no different to a woman falling across a county line.”

“Disorganisation, not finishing dealing with one case before signing off, lack of coordination between departments. A seeming inability to listen unless the patient becomes irate”

“Waiting list times are getting worse. When you ask for help, you have already gone through all the “at home” things you can do but you will just be referred back to these mainly through website links or leaflets. When it gets to this point you can be desperate for help now. This puts excessive strain on individuals, their families both physically and mentally. Early years support in Bracknell is terrible - particularly the children's development centre. They are not ND affirming and do not give advice suitable for ND children - very basic old school type parenting advice. As a carer I was dismissed for almost 2 years regarding my child's autism and told to wait out and that I had no experience with ND children so I wouldn't know despite clearly having a ND child. Once

we received a diagnosis they were acting like I should be shocked when I had been asking for support for a long time and then was just given a leaflet and no ongoing support plan”

“I am genuinely losing hope for my own safety within my care and feel regularly that concerning symptoms are dismissed due to my age.”

Summary of findings: GP services

Respondents were predominantly working age adults, with a substantial proportion reporting a disability or long-term condition. Across the sample, difficulty accessing GP services emerged as a dominant concern.

The most frequently reported barriers to GP access included telephone congestion, inability to secure appointments within a reasonable timeframe, digital only triage systems, and lack of continuity with the same clinician. Disabled respondents consistently reported poorer access and lower perceived support from GP practices compared with non-disabled respondents.

Free text responses highlighted the cumulative burden of navigating fragmented services, with participants describing feelings of dismissal, exhaustion, and inequity linked to place of residence. Many working adults reported compromising their health due to inflexible appointment systems, underscoring the intersection of employment and access to care.

Overall, findings indicate that healthcare inequalities in regards to GP care in this sample are driven less by individual behaviour and more by structural features of service design, particularly appointment systems, continuity of care, and place-based variation.

Summary of findings: hospital-based services

Across the sample, respondents reported substantial difficulty accessing hospital-based NHS services. Long waiting times for appointments, investigations, and procedures were frequently described, alongside poor communication regarding referral status and expected timelines.

Respondents highlighted fragmentation between primary and secondary care, reporting that information provided to GPs was not always reflected in hospital encounters. Disabled respondents and those with complex needs described particular challenges navigating hospital environments, including accessibility barriers and insufficient reasonable adjustments.

Travel and transport emerged as a notable barrier, especially for individuals required to attend distant hospital sites or manage frequent appointments. Mental health, learning disability, and neurodiversity-related needs were often perceived as inadequately supported within hospital settings, contributing to feelings of distress and exclusion.

Overall, findings suggest that inequalities in access to hospital care are shaped by systemic factors, including waiting list management, service coordination, accessibility, and communication, rather than by individual patient characteristics alone.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this survey.

System-wide recommendations map: End-to-end care pathway

Stage 1: Entry to care (GP)

Main inequality risks

- Access bottlenecks such as phone congestion, digital-only triage and limited appointment availability.

Recommended actions

- Introduce call-back systems and assisted digital or non-digital booking routes.
- Expand flexible appointment times, including evenings or weekends.
- Improve continuity for people with complex or long-term needs.

Lead / supporting organisations: Primary Care Networks and GP practices (lead), supported by the Integrated Care Board and VCSE digital inclusion services.

Stage 2: Referral and triage

Main inequality risks

- Poor coordination and lack of feedback during referral stages increase patient burden and anxiety.

Recommended actions

- Standardise referral acknowledgement and expected timelines.
- Reduce repeated storytelling through shared information and care plans.
- Provide proactive updates to patients during referral waiting periods.

Lead / supporting organisations: Integrated Care Board (lead), supported by NHS Trusts and GP practices.

Stage 3: Hospital attendance

Main inequality risks

- Long waits, accessibility issues, travel demands and distress for people with mental health, learning disability or neurodiversity needs.

Recommended actions

- Provide accessible booking systems and appointment information.
- Ensure reasonable adjustments are delivered consistently.
- Improve transport and parking support.

Lead / supporting organisations: NHS Trusts (lead), supported by Local Authorities, the Integrated Care Board and VCSE partners.

Stage 4: Treatment and follow-up

Main inequality risks

- Fragmented follow-up and delayed communication back to primary care undermine outcomes.

Recommended actions

- Ensure timely discharge summaries and clear follow-up plans delivered using appropriate communication tools (email/voice memo/paper copy depending on patient needs).
- Provide patient-friendly information using appropriate communication tools so that patients can refer back to what was said on next steps.
- Introduce care coordination for people with ongoing or complex needs.

Lead / supporting organisations: NHS Trusts and Primary Care Networks (joint lead), supported by community services and the Integrated Care Board.